

SOCIAL SCIENCES

COMMUNICATIVE ASPECTS OF THE GEORGIAN SOCIAL ADVERTISEMENT

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Abstract

For the last decades reflection of the social issues in the dimension of mass communication of social issues became actual in the contemporary world. Rising of social problems, their discussing and searching of the ways of their settlement is the key step of development of the society, that has been charged on the social advertising successfully throughout the history of its development.

Social advertisement, in its essence, is responsible for supporting of the welfare (benefit), rising of the social awareness, and, without any prejudice, it serves to charitable purposes. Social advertisement clearly demonstrates harmful sides and opportunities for their correction.

It is the well-known fact that different communicative means are applied in the conventional advertisement for having an impact on viewers. The article is targeted at studying and distinguishing of communicative aspects and emotional effects in advertising social video clips.

Theory of agenda is used as the theoretic frame in the research, and characteristic research – as a method of the research. It considers analyzing of the empiric field based on the methods of characteristic content and visual analysis, by means of which trends, means of expressions and communicative factors existing in the advertising social video clips will be appeared.

Keywords: social advertisement, communicative aspects, media effects.

Preamble

Advertisement became a companion of our life. In addition to it, all significant events of the last two centuries had been reflected in it. As for the social advertisement, it became the best mean for discussing of social problems and searching for the way of their settlement. Advertisement, with the account of different epochs and trends, has different challengers, but in any case, it reflects social problems being relevant for a definite period of time.

As opposed to commercial advertisement, social advertisement is targeted at rising of social awareness, supporting of welfare, making of one's behavior more positive.

Here, we would like to mention, that while creating of the advertisement a particular attention always was paid on communicational-psychological factors to enable it to have an affect on viewers easier. Despite of the fact that the target of the social advertisement is absolutely different from the target of commercial one, it, in any case, contains psychological effects, particularly emotional background.

Actual social problems and ways of their settlement are read in the contemporary Georgian advertising social video clips. All this will be demonstrated in the represented article with its characteristic features, trends and moods. Proceeding from the stated, we can state that communicational phenomena of the social advertisement is a mirror of the Georgian reality which, in its turn, tries to play on the viewers' emotions and to affect them. In this case, it really has kind purposes, such as: decreasing of the number of traffic accidents, prevention of violence committed against women, ending of pandemics and others.

Review of literature

The industrial revolution, in parallel with increasing of production, created a large demand on advertising, being a kind of mass communication. As a result of it, since the 19th century, it, together with its large scaled context, turned into the one of the key characteristic features of the urbanistic-industrial society proceeding from the fact that advertising directly reflects current events and problems (Defleur & Dennis, 2009).

On top of all, advertising is characterized as a valuable mean of delivery of information on any product, service or idea by non-personal way. It is disseminated by payable means, and a fine advertisement is reflected on realization of the advertised product (Kotler & Armstrong, 2007). In this case, we talk about the commercial advertisement targeted at gaining of more profits, improving of one's image or rising awareness.

However, unlike the stated, a target and assignation of the advertisement estimated on the non-commercial profit is different. According to the guiding recommendations connected with spreading of a social ad in the broadcasting network, the social advertising should serve to supporting of the social benefit, reaching of charitable aims, rising awareness of the society regarding significant social problems and/or or changing of the positive opinion of the social behavior (Georgian Legislative Herald, 2005).

We can say that social advertising is aimed at attracting of one's attention on a definite problem which is actual for a definite period of time and needs to be resolved. A part of the society, frequently, closes its eyes on the existing reality and does not search for the ways of its resolving. For instance, drug addiction, traf-

fic safety, homeless children and others. Social advertisement was created for identifying of a problem and improving of the state (Karkashadze, 2012).

Unless the social advertisement established aims formed recently, it had passed a history of the long-termed origination and development. It made its first steps in the USA and Great Britain, which are the birthplace of the first social ad. In 1906, the “American Citizens Association” created the first social ad about “Niagara” and called the population for protecting of the waterfall as activity of the power company incurred a damage to it.

Sometimes later social advertising became more popular and during the first world war it turned into the key mean of communication. The states involved in the war were applying it as the weapon to obtain the population’s support. For example, one of the famous slogans in America was “You are needed by the American Army”, in which the Uncle Sam called the population for joining the Army, the next is the ad created in Britain – “Your state needs you”.

After ending of the war, the area of the social advertising covered more positive issues, but the key issue of the civil problematics was connected with health care.

By the end of the 20th century, we face many new issues and high-budgeted social ads appear in the USA. One of the examples is rising awareness on AID “You may become the AIDS carrier”; about traffic safety – “Abstinence while driving the car”.

Recently we can say, that Georgia faces multiple social problems, efficient ways of their solving are frequently met solely in social ads which help us to conclude if which important problems are actual in the country in a definite period of time. They are directed to rising awareness in society and improving of the existing state.

Social advertisement may be placed in all means of mass communication – television, radio, press, internet, that is supplemented with the means of external advertising, such as public transport, banners and others. However, only the Public Broadcaster is obliged to place a social ad in its live free of charge that considers 90 seconds at least in three hours (Georgian Legislative Herald, 2005) as the Public Broadcaster is solely charged with the most important function to provide the society with the content relevant with social interests and released from political and commercial effects. Accordingly, all this considers social advertising as well. Here, it is remarkable, that a social ad may be recorded by a state authority, NGO, charitable organization and private business as well.

Social advertising, on the way of its development, has obtained several contents that nowadays can be classified by us as follows:

- Advertisement which narrates about definite rules of life, their advantages and benefits, or, in contrary, reflects a negative impact of drug addition, alcohol and tobacco consumption;
- Advertisement devoted to ecology, nature and animals’ protection and care;
- Advertisement which is directed to constitutional obligations of people;

- Advertisements absorbed with patriotic attitudes.

Besides, there are several characteristic features of the social advertising which differs it from the commercial advertising and enriches it with additional values:

- Positive attitude;
- A subject of the ad is a human being, but not a subject;
- Unifies the society, has an influence on its majority;
- Is based on the socially adoptable norms;
- Encourages people in involving in the process of settling of problems and motivates them (Melnikova, 2010).

Despite of the above-mentioned, we should not forget, that the ad, in its essence, is directed to awaking of a desire to buy a concrete service or product. It should attract, to rise interest of a consumer and due to this fact different psychological aspects are applied. For the purpose of making of a definite influence the advertisement may be rational and emotional. The first one is based on the trustful argument and delivers information. The emotional one is focused on the world of senses, emotions, and has an impact by means of a definite idea.

But how the issue is posed in case of a social advertisement?

Emotion is an internal state of a human being which means our relevant attitude regarding this or that event or object, for example, anger, fright, happiness, sadness and others.

While talking about psychological phenomena and communicative aspects we should separately discuss emotional factors which, in scopes of the advertisement, have an effect on people. According to the Plutchik’s psycho-evolutional theory of emotions, emotions help people in adapting with the environment that stimulates his behavior. Based on the theory there are eight emotions: anger, fright, sadness, cheer, hate, surprise, expectation (interest), trust. (Plutchik, 1991).

Plutchik suggests us a link of development of main emotions that, consequently, leads a person to a definite action. The stated chain looks like as follows: a stimulus (external event) causes perceiving, which, in its turn, is processed cognitively. As a result, a specific emotional background appears and causes behavior (Plutchik, 1991). Advertisement frequently effects the consumers’ emotions. On top of the above-mentioned eight main emotions, which are strong triggers of desires and responses, psychologists separate additional emotions: love, pleasure, striving for grandeur, credibility.

Let’s discuss each of them separately:

Fright is a very strong emotion, characterized with creation of the state containing danger and having a function of self-survival. The ad may use the word “fright” to complicate any unpleasant event, and then to show the outcome from the existing difficult situation;

Anger is a response on the created problem targeted at its eradicating;

Cheer has a motivation of reproduction and leaving descendants;

Losing of a person brings a sadness, - the emotion which unites the people surrounding you;

Trust appears when, in a definite situation, we meet a person we know and simultaneously strive for strengthening of a closer relation with him or her;

The object unpleasant for us originates a negative reaction and an emotion of hate targeted at waiving of something that carries a potential danger for us.

Expectation (interest) is characteristic for the circumstance when we meet something new, an alien, indefinite. We are encouraged by an interest and desire to get acquainted with the new and our behavior is directed to studying.

Surprise is a response on any unknown, unexpected object. Simultaneously a person tries to understand the extent of danger coming from it and whether he may stay quietly.

Pleasure is the emotion which is experienced by a human being when he/she is in a pleasant situation; accordingly, its purpose is to create a positive energy that after fulfillment of a kind of action will force us to represent it in a desirable manner.

The emotion of love awakes a skill of taking care over another person, something that can manage a person. And for the people occupying a particular place in our life, we wish the best.

The emotion of striving for grandeur awakes other emotions, such as proudness, good attitude, misappropriation, striving for a better life.

Credibility – the state when internally one needs a reliable person who will approve our choice. Frequently such person is a well-known individual entrusted by a large part of people; accordingly, his truth is never doubtful.

Theoretic frame

A theory of agenda

Founders of the theory of agenda of the mass media are Maxwell Jacobs and Donald Show; they were the first who mentioned the link between the content existing in media and requirements of the auditory. Determination of prioritized issues and social interests solely underlay creating of the mass media communication field.

Accordingly, the theory of agenda assists to the mass communication to identify social needs and actual problems. Proceeding from the fact that, in social ads, we see reflection of the social routine problems, it seems to us that using of the theory of agenda is relevant as it is the proper way of selecting of this or that problem and volume of time to be spent on it.

Method of research

The method of research used for the stated article is the qualitative content analysis and visual analysis which enable us to observe the social advertising and to analyze the content expressed in it.

Visual material, while representing of the social life, narrates about the people and events represented in it. Actually, based on the visual analysis we can observe the process of formation and transformation of the issue being under research. The selected method is relevant while reviewing of the ad as it suggests role-related

models of identity to the viewer, tries to have an impact on formation of attitudes and to stimulate a definite action.

Discussion

The Georgian reality is not rich with social advertisements, but the country stands in front of multiple social problems. For instance, one of the problems is violence against women. The video clip devoted to this problem was represented by the Ministry of Internal Affairs and its main aim was to create a trust towards the state authorities among the women who are the victims of violence.⁶ Primarily, we should state that the above-mentioned advertisement is very emotional and refers to the totally sensitive problem; accordingly, it awakes too many different emotions.

The social advertisement focused on decreasing of violence against women spread by the state named “Power to the Trust” awakes the emotion of fright as a clear problem exists and the way of its resolving is determined, - to address to the Ministry of Internal Affairs timely if you are a victim. A man worn in the police uniform being a representative of the authority tells to the hero being a victim of violence: “You should trust me, tell me the truth enabling us to help you”. Here, an attempt of awaking of the emotion of trust is made. Simultaneously, it is supplemented with a feeling of finding of the authority. A viewer obtains two feelings in relation to the “rescuer”, represented by the MIA, who is worth of trust for sake of survival and overcoming of fright. On top of all, he becomes the authority whose word and promise coincides with the truth without any doubt.

Finally, this video clip is ending with the victim’s cry that, unambiguously, causes a feeling of sadness among viewers. All this, according to the Plutchik, can be explained by the emotions which can unite the people surrounding the person. To eradicate the risen problem, it is necessary to rise awareness in the society as well as among the women being victims of violence to provide their timely appealing to relevant authorities; thus, the feeling of sadness exactly complied with the aim.

Another one social problem which must be resolved and to which multiple video clips had been devoted, is driving a vehicle in a drunken state. This circumstance frequently causes accidents, and accordingly we should rise awareness of drivers and to show them the extent of danger in case of driving of a vehicle in a drunken state. In the video clip, three children are running to the vehicle, sit in and actuate the car. In the same place the cadre with children is replaced with the cadre of drunken young men. Accordingly, children are replaced by those men who activate the vehicle, drive it, and finally the viewer hears a noise of signal which probably indicates to the collision of cars.

In the stated social ad only the background indicating voice is heard: “The drunken man is the same as the child who does not understand the extent of danger from driving the car and if we never place the child on the wheel, why should we place adults in such state – think about it.”⁷ Several emotional factors are used in the advertisement, for instance, love. It awakes a skill

⁶ <https://bit.ly/3BBD3P4> (last seen 09.10.2024)

⁷ <https://bit.ly/3Y4B25s> (last seen 05.10.2024)

of taking care over other people that we have towards children. It is exactly the time when people have a feeling of responsibility towards them and wish all the best for them. Here, it is worth to mention the emotion of hate which is designed to force the person to waive something that is carrying a damage for him. Accordingly, in this definite case the accident is followed with the fright of what can occur with us or other people being valuable for us.

For the purpose of decreasing of accidents other Georgian social advertisements were created, for instance the ad with the title “Do not turn over your own life.” In the clip the main hero is a male driver who reminds the time carried with his wife and small children.⁸ The video clip is followed with the background voice which is ended with the text: “It seems to be that the past can not be returned as the thing we talk about is the past, do not turnover your own life.” In the cadre we see a vehicle turned over during the accident. Finally, the voice reports about the statistics of fatal accidents to rise the emotion of anger among viewers, to show the large scale of this problem and create a desire of participating in its eradication. In the same advertisement the emotion of sadness is used which may unite the surrounded people, that happens in this video clip reflecting losing of one’s family.

Another significant social problem refers to the human health. The last such issue was the pandemics, to which multiple social clips had been devoted to it. Proceeding from the fact that, majorly, the whole state and the whole world was locked down we meet only graphic video clips. For instance, it provided us with the safety rules necessary to prevent spreading of the COVID 19⁹; sometimes it taught us how to use the face mask;¹⁰ and/or acquaint us with implementing/ removing of the restrictions acting in the state¹¹. Following that the process of vaccination was launched and the stated advertisements were supplemented with another one – “The vaccine protects us.”¹² Its aim was informing of the society about positive sides and benefits of the vaccine. Accordingly, it encourages people to enroll into the process of eradication of this problem, in this case the pandemics, besides it suggests a way of settling of this problem – vaccination.

For the same purpose, another ad was created for encouraging of vaccination – “Make a vaccine and breath out.”¹³ It illustrates key personages who had breath out after overcoming of any problem in different circumstances. Finally, it is how a person may breathe out after making a vaccine and to return to the routine he enjoyed before (gathering together and enjoying seeing each other).

It strengthens definite new social norms; it is distinguished by its positive attitude and is absorbed with

the cheer of the emotion of victory. It also contains a clearly expressed emotion of pleasure which is enjoyed by a person for a long time and it is the main idea reminded by the advertisement to the viewers – what the life looked like before the pandemics, what was the extent of happiness and what one should do to return to that life.

Conclusion

Against the background of the theoretic frame and based on analyzing of the empiric field we can say that the Georgian social advertisements carry more emotional character and are not rational; they reflect the problems existing in the state and use psychological effects, mainly the emotional background.

In the summary we would like to separate the key emotion which is awoken in a person by the social ad – fright, anger, sadness, sometimes cheer, that depends upon the suggested method of resolving of the problem.

The social advertisements, with the account of communicative and psychological aspects, integrate the society around a definite problem and encourage them to take a part in its eradication. The accent is made on the people, events, but not on the subjects or products. Significance is assigned to the social welfare and rising of its awareness.

The social advertising has obtained means of manipulating, using emotions creates own narrative, tries to have an impact on the viewers, but serves to the kind purposes.

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⁸ <https://bit.ly/3ZV2QvS> (last seen 01.10.2024)

⁹ <https://bit.ly/401Bgx0> (last seen 07.10.2024)

¹⁰ <https://bit.ly/4dYh7LP> (last seen 28.09.2024)

¹¹ <https://bit.ly/4dNxfiW> (last seen 28.09.2024)

¹² <https://bit.ly/3BEvpU9> (last seen 25.09.2024)

¹³ <https://bit.ly/3U3HuIW> (last seen 25.09.2024)